

Generalized Estimation of Stress-Strength Reliability $R = P(X > Y)$

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the point estimation of the stress-strength reliability coefficient $R = P(X > Y)$ in the case of two distributions that their functional forms are known but depend on unknown parameters. Previous studies in this field estimated R by evaluating the exact value of the double integral and then estimating the apparent parameter using methods such as maximum likelihood estimation. Due to the large number of candidate distributions available for data modeling, many research papers addressing this issue have emerged over the past three decades. In this paper, we establish a general model for R , which is applicable to any pair of continuous statistical distributions. The estimation process led to three new estimators for R , all of which rely on the cumulative distribution functions of the assumed random variables. The consistency property for each estimator is established and also their performances for finite sample sizes are investigated by conducting a limited simulation study. The numerical results demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed method, comparing to the current estimators, the performances of the proposed estimators is very promising. Although the generality of the model may lead to some loss of efficiency, this loss is small in most cases.

Key words: Stress-Strength reliability; Point Estimation Method; Expectation; Parametric distributions; Relative bias; Relative mean square error; Efficiency.

MSC: 62F10; 62F12.

1. Introduction

Reliability plays a vital role in the economic feasibility of systems, which refers to the probability that a product, system, or service will perform its intended function satisfactorily for a certain period or in a specific environment without failure. Small changes in the assumed models of random variables X (strength) and Y (stress) can significantly affect the probability of failure. The strength-stress analysis models this scenario. The strength of the component is described by a random variable X , while the stress it is subjected to is described by another random variable Y . When the applied stress exceeds the strength of the component, failure occurs. The reliability coefficient can be expressed as $R = P(X > Y)$, which is the probability that the strength exceeds the stress. This reliability parameter is a vital concept in various engineering fields that deal with material strength, structural integrity, and system design under stress.. It also has diverse applications, such as rocket engines, earthquake resistance, and the response of leprosy patients to drugs (Kotz *et al.*, 2003).

Let X and Y be two random variables with continuous probability density functions (pdfs) $f_X(x; \theta)$ and $f_Y(y; \delta)$ respectively, where θ and δ are unknown parameters, each of which may be a vector. For more convenience, take $f_X(x) = f_X(x; \theta)$ and $f_Y(y) = f_Y(y; \delta)$ and let $f(x, y)$ be the joint pdf of X and Y , then the reliability coefficient $R = P(X > Y)$ is expressed as,

$$R = P(X > Y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_y^{\infty} f(x, y) dx dy = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^x f(x, y) dy dx.$$

If X and Y are two independent random variables, then

$$R = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_y^{\infty} f_X(x) f_Y(y) dx dy = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^x f_X(x) f_Y(y) dy dx.$$

It is important to note that the coefficient R is an unknown parameter because the result of any of the previous integrals, when exist, is a function of the parameters θ and δ . Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1} be a random sample drawn from $f_X(x)$ and Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_{n_2} be another independent random sample from $f_Y(y)$. The stress-strength parameter R can be estimated using two main approaches, which are parametric and non-parametric methods. In the parametric method, we assume that the shape of the data distribution is known, but it relies on unknown parameters that need to be estimated. In this case, these parameters, and thus parameter R are usually estimated using classical methods such as, maximum likelihood (ML) method, method of moments and uniformly minimum variance unbiased method. In contrast, the non-parametric method is used when the shape of distribution is unknown or difficult to determine.

Some researchers have used non-parametric methods for statistical inferences on R . Kim *et al.* (1994) investigated R in cases where censored observations occur for the strength variable, without assuming knowledge of stress or strength distributions. Baklizi and Eidous (2006) examined both point and interval estimation of R using kernel density estimators for the

distributions of stress (X) and strength (Y). Eidous and Baklizi (2004) Eidous and Baklizi (2004) and Montoyal and Rubio (2014) discussed the same problem when X and Y are not independent. The well-known non-parametric estimator frequently used is the Mann-Whitney estimator (\hat{R}_{MA}) (Lehmann, 1975), which is given by,

$$\hat{R}_{MW} = \frac{1}{n_1 n_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \psi(x_i, y_j),$$

where $\psi(x_i, y_j) = 1$, if $x_i > y_j$ and zero otherwise. This estimator has been included in our simulation study in Section (5) of this paper for comparison purposes.

Many studies have employed parametric approaches to estimate R under different distributions, including exponential (Baklizi, 2003), generalized exponential (Kundu and Gupta, 2005; Raqab et al., 2008), Weibull (Kundu and Raqab, 2009), Burr type III (Mokhlis, 2005), generalized Pareto (Rezaeia et al., 2010), double Lomax (Punathumpambath, 2011), two-parameter Weibull model based on records (Baklizi, 2012), generalized logistic (Asgharzadeh et al., 2013), inverse Rayleigh (Rao et al., 2013), exponentiated Fréchet (Inverse Weibull) (Rao et al., 2016), two-parameter generalized exponential (Asgharzadeh et al., 2017), exponentiated Fréchet distribution using Type-II censored data (Nadeb et al., 2019), Rayleigh (Abu-Moussa et al., 2021), inverse Rayleigh (Kalaf et al., 2021), Rayleigh and half-normal (Alamri et al., 2021), generalized Gompertz (Ciftci et al., 2023) and two-parameter Pareto distribution (Long and Jiang). Recently, Quintino et al. (2024a) examined R by considering some asymmetric distributions and Quintino et al. (2024b) estimated R under Birnbaum–Saunders Components, obtained a general results using a simulation and real data.

Studies have advanced in the analysis of stress strength reliability - as we have seen - by presenting new distributions, estimation methods, and inferential techniques, making their applications broader in various scientific and industrial fields. This has enriched the understanding of strength-stress analysis by integrating diverse perspectives and methodologies. Additionally, there are many studies that have introduced other distributions. Besides the references mentioned, readers can refer to the sources within them for further studies in this field.

Traditionally, most studies that used the parametric approach to estimate R imposed certain constraints on the parameters of the assumed pair of distributions (see for example, Rezaeia et al., 2010 and Asgharzadeh et al., 2013). Although such assumptions allow for the precise evaluation of the integral that appears in the form of R , and thus facilitate the estimation process, these assumptions diminish the practical significance of these distributions. Without these constraints, the evaluation of the integral remains complex, making the estimation process neither straightforward nor simple.

In this paper, we proposed a new and general technique for estimating R by expressing the integral of R as the expectation of a certain function. Instead of estimating the integral directly, we estimate the resulting expectations using the statistical method of moments. The resulting

estimators are given in a general form, allowing their use regardless of the assumed distributions and without imposing any restrictions on their parameters.

2. General Model for $R = P(X > Y)$

The reliability measure of the stress-strength R for the independent random variables X and Y can be expressed as follows,

$$R_1 = P(X > Y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x) \left(\int_{-\infty}^x f_Y(y) dy \right) dx.$$

The internal integral is a cumulative distribution function (CDF) of Y , which is denoted as $F_Y(x)$. Therefore, we can rewrite R_1 as follows,

$$R_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x) F_Y(x) dx.$$

Moreover, R can be rewritten as follows,

$$R_2 = P(X > Y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_Y(y) \left(\int_y^{\infty} f_X(x) dx \right) dy.$$

Since the internal integral is $1 - F_X(y)$, then we get,

$$R_2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_Y(y)(1 - F_X(y)) dy = 1 - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_Y(y) F_X(y) dy.$$

Accordingly, both R_1 and R_2 can be expressed as an expected value as follows,

$$R_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x) F_Y(x) dx = E(F_Y(X))$$

$$R_2 = 1 - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_Y(y) F_X(y) dy = 1 - E(F_X(Y)).$$

Since $R = R_1 = R_2$, we can define a more general formulation for R by taking the average of R_1 and R_2 . That is,

$$R_3 = \frac{R_1 + R_2}{2}.$$

In terms of expected value, R can be expressed as follows,

$$R_3 = \frac{E(F_Y(X)) - E(F_X(Y)) + 1}{2}.$$

Note: The expression $R_1 = E(F_Y(X))$ represents the expected value (mean) of the CDF of Y evaluated at X . Similarly, $1 - R_2 = E(F_X(Y))$ represents the expected value (mean) of the CDF of X at Y .

3. Estimation of $R = P(X > Y)$

Throughout this paper, we assume that $\hat{\delta}$ and $\hat{\theta}$ are the maximum likelihood (ML) estimators of δ and θ respectively. The quantity

$$R_1 = E(F_Y(X; \delta))$$

represents the mean of $F_Y(X; \delta)$. To estimate R_1 , we employ the method of moments while incorporating $\hat{\delta}$ as the ML estimator of δ . Given a random sample X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1} , we estimate R_1 using the sample mean of $F_Y(X_1; \hat{\delta})$, $F_Y(X_2; \hat{\delta})$, \dots , $F_Y(X_{n_1}; \hat{\delta})$ leading to the estimator,

$$\hat{R}_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \hat{\delta}).$$

Here, the function F_Y is the CDF of a random variable Y evaluated at each X_k using the ML estimator $\hat{\delta}$ of δ that obtained from the second sample Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_{n_2} . Applying the same technique, we estimate the quantity $R_2 = 1 - E(F_X(Y; \theta))$ by,

$$\hat{R}_2 = 1 - \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} F_X(Y_k; \hat{\theta}).$$

The function F_X is the CDF of a random variable X evaluated at each Y_k using the ML estimator $\hat{\theta}$ of θ that obtained from the first sample X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1} . Finally, we estimate the quantity $R_3 = (E(F_Y(X)) - E(F_X(Y)) + 1)/2$ by averaging \hat{R}_1 and \hat{R}_2 , leading to,

$$\hat{R}_3 = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \hat{\delta}) - \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} F_X(Y_k; \hat{\theta}) \right].$$

This estimator combines the information from both, providing a balanced estimator for R . To use the above three estimators of R , the CDFs of X and Y , as well as the ML estimators of θ and δ need to be determined. It is worth noting that the case where no information is available about the shapes of the two distributions has been discussed by Eidous (2025), who recommended nonparametric methods, specifically, histogram and kernel density estimators, for estimating R .

4. Consistency of the Estimators \hat{R}_1 , \hat{R}_2 and \hat{R}_3

To establish the consistency of estimators \hat{R}_1 , \hat{R}_2 and \hat{R}_3 , we need to show that each one of them converges in probability to R . Assume that $E(F_Y(X; \delta))$ is finite, then using weak law of large numbers (WLLN) to obtain,

$$\frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \delta) \xrightarrow{p} E(F_Y(X; \delta)).$$

Given that $\hat{\delta} \xrightarrow{p} \delta$, and assume that $F_Y(X; \delta)$ is a continuous in δ , then by using continuous mapping theorem,

$$F_Y(X_k; \hat{\delta}) \xrightarrow{p} F_Y(X_k; \delta)$$

for each k , which implies,

$$\frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \hat{\delta}) \xrightarrow{p} \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \delta).$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \hat{\delta}) - \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \delta) \xrightarrow{p} 0.$$

Because $\frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \delta) \xrightarrow{p} E(F_Y(X; \delta))$ then by using Slutsky's theorem we obtain,

$$\hat{R}_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} F_Y(X_k; \hat{\delta}) \xrightarrow{p} E(F_Y(X; \delta)) = R.$$

Similarly to the above discussion, and by assuming that $E(F_X(Y; \theta))$ is finite and continuous in θ , we can easily show that $\hat{R}_2 \xrightarrow{p} R$ when $\hat{\theta} \xrightarrow{p} \theta$. Additionally, we can combine both results to show that $\hat{R}_3 \xrightarrow{p} R$.

This proves that the sample means of $F_Y(X; \hat{\delta})$ and $F_X(Y; \hat{\theta})$ are consistent estimators of $E(F_Y(X; \delta))$ and $1 - E(F_X(Y; \theta))$ respectively, thereby establishing the consistency of \hat{R}_1 , \hat{R}_2 and \hat{R}_3 as estimators of R .

5. Simulation Study for Evaluating Estimators of R

A Simulation study is conducted to compare and evaluate the performance of the proposed estimators \hat{R}_1 , \hat{R}_2 and \hat{R}_3 of $R = P(X > Y)$ described in Section (3). All simulation results are calculated using *Mathematica Version 7* for sample sizes $(n_1, n_2) = (50, 50)$ and $(100, 200)$. The data x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n_1} for the random variable X and y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n_2} for the random variable Y are generated from three different pair of distributions: normal, Weibull and generalized-Pareto. For each pair of distributions, two different parameter settings are considered to ensure that one of the two values of R less than 0.5 and the other one is greater than 0.5 toward 1. Let $N(\alpha, \beta)$, $W(\alpha, \beta)$ and $GP(\alpha, \beta)$ denotes the normal, Weibull and generalized-

Pareto distributions respectively, each characterized by two parameters. We examine the following cases:

Normal:

- Case (1): $X \sim N(0, 1)$ and $Y \sim N(-1.75, 0.75)$, with the exact $R = 0.9192$.
- Case (2): $X \sim N(0, 1)$ and $Y \sim N(1.5, 4.0)$, with the exact $R = 0.3581$.

Weibull:

- Case (1): $X \sim W(1, 1)$ and $Y \sim W(1, 0.1)$, with the exact $R = 0.9091$.
- Case (2): $X \sim W(1, 1)$ and $Y \sim W(1, 2.5)$, with the exact $R = 0.2857$.

Generalized-Pareto:

- Case (1): $X \sim GP(2, 1)$ and $Y \sim GP(2, 8)$ with the exact $R = 0.8889$.
- Case (2): $X \sim GP(2, 2)$ and $Y \sim GP(2, 1)$ with the exact $R = 0.3333$.

By selecting normal (symmetric, baseline case), Weibull (skewed, reliability-focused) and generalized-Pareto (extreme values, heavy tails), our simulation study effectively tests estimator performance across a wide range of realistic data scenarios. This ensures that the conclusions drawn are robust, generalizable, and applicable to diverse practical problems. For this simulation study, other scenarios and cases were considered, including sample sizes smaller and larger than those used in this study. Additionally, cases for the three distributions with different parameter values were examined to ensure both an increase and a decrease in the value of parameter R . However, we found that the conclusions drawn in this study remain consistent, and therefore, we have limited the inclusion, only, to the cases presented in this study.

For each combination of (n_1, n_2) and parent distributions, 1000 independent replications of samples X and Y are generated (i.e. $Rep = 1000$).

The proposed estimators together with the nonparametric Mann-Whitney estimator, \hat{R}_{MW} (see Section 1) are considered. Furthermore, the ML estimators of R that previously developed in the literature in the case of normal, Weibull and generalized-Pareto distributions are also included. These estimators are denoted as \hat{R}_{JA} (Jacobs *et al.*, 2015), \hat{R}_{MC} (McCool, 1991) and \hat{R}_{RE} (Rezaei *et al.*, 2010), with their respective formulas given below:

Jacobs *et al.* (2015) estimator with pair normal distributions:

$$\hat{R}_{JA} = \Phi\left(\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2}}\right).$$

McCool (1991) estimator with pair Weibull distributions ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 1$):

$$\hat{R}_{MC} = \frac{\bar{x}}{\bar{x} + \bar{y}}.$$

Rezaei *et al.* (2010) estimator with pair generalized-Pareto distributions ($\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 2$):

$$\hat{R}_{RE} = \frac{\hat{\alpha}_2}{\hat{\alpha}_1 + \hat{\alpha}_2},$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_1 = n_1 / \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \ln(1 + 2x_i)$ and $\hat{\alpha}_2 = n_2 / \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \ln(1 + 2y_j)$.

The investigation and comparison of these estimators are based on their relative bias (*RB*), relative mean square error (*RMSE*) and efficiency (*EFF*) of with respect to Mann-Whitney estimator, \hat{R}_{MA} . These measures are computed by using the following formulas,

$$RB = \frac{\hat{E}(\text{estimator}) - \text{exact } R}{\text{exact } R},$$

$$RME = \frac{\sqrt{\widehat{MSE}(\text{estimator})}}{\text{exact } R},$$

$$EFF = \frac{\widehat{MSE}(\text{estimator})}{\widehat{MSE}(\text{Mann - whitney estimator})},$$

where

$$\hat{E}(\hat{R}) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{Rep} \hat{R}_{(j)}}{Rep},$$

$$\widehat{MSE}(\hat{R}) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{Rep} (\hat{R}_{(j)} - E(\hat{R}))^2}{Rep}.$$

Here, $\hat{R}_{(j)}$ represents the value of the estimator computed for a given sample at iteration j , where, $j = 1, 2, \dots, Rep = 1000$.

6. Simulation Results

The simulation results, presented in Tables 1-3, lead to the following general conclusions:

- For all estimators considered, the absolute relative bias (*|RB|*) tends to decrease as the sample size increases. Similarly, the root mean square error (*RMSE*) also declines with larger samples, indicating improved estimator performance with increasing sample size.
- While the performance of the Mann-Whitney estimator \hat{R}_{MW} is generally acceptable, the other estimators outperform it across all cases considered.
- The efficiency (*EFF*) values for all estimators are greater than 1, suggesting that they outperform the Mann-Whitney estimator, \hat{R}_{MW} . This result is expected since the Mann-Whitney estimator is non-parametric and does not rely on distributional assumptions.
- Among the three proposed estimators (\hat{R}_1 , \hat{R}_2 and \hat{R}_3), \hat{R}_1 performs better than \hat{R}_2 when the true value of R is small, while the reverse holds when R is large. The estimator \hat{R}_3 provides a balanced performance between \hat{R}_1 and \hat{R}_2 , regardless of whether R is small or

large. In general, the proposed estimator \hat{R}_3 performs well across different cases and sample sizes.

- Based on RMSE and EFF values, the estimator \hat{R}_{Lit} demonstrates the best performance among all considered estimators. This is likely because \hat{R}_{Lit} is derived using the exact value of R under the assumption of interested distribution. However, at least one of the proposed estimators yield results similar to \hat{R}_{Lit} , particularly as sample sizes increase. This supports the effectiveness of the general estimation model for R .

In conclusion and despite the fact that the three estimators developed in the literature for estimating R —namely, \hat{R}_{JA} (for normal distributions), \hat{R}_{MC} (for Weibull distributions), and \hat{R}_{RE} (for generalized-Pareto distributions)—each perform better than the others within their respective distribution contexts, their applicability remains limited. This is because each estimator is only valid under specific dependence distributions. Furthermore, some of these estimators impose additional restrictions on the parameters of those distributions. For instance, \hat{R}_{MC} can only be applied to paired Weibull distributions when the two shape parameters are equal. The same assumption is required for \hat{R}_{RE} . In contrast, the proposed estimators place no such restrictions on distribution parameters. They only require that the distribution parameters be estimated using any reliable method, such as the maximum likelihood method.

7. Discussion

In the literature on estimating the stress-strength reliability coefficient $R = P(X > Y)$, we encountered numerous studies, potentially in the dozens or even hundreds. While the practical significance of this topic is undeniable, many of these studies exhibit a high degree of similarity, with the primary distinction being the choice of the assumed pair of statistical distributions, often drawn from the same family. In this paper, we introduce a general formulation for R and propose novel estimators for this formulation. These estimators are versatile, applicable to any pair of statistical distributions, even those from different families, without the limitations commonly found in traditional methods. In addition, we show that the proposed estimators satisfy an essential property of any good estimator: consistency. Despite this, the performance and effectiveness of these estimators, when applied to finite sample sizes, do not yet match the efficiency of existing estimators, as demonstrated in the simulation study. However, a crucial takeaway is that the estimators found in the literature have a very narrow scope of application, relying on strict assumptions that may not always hold in practical scenarios. On the other hand, the proposed estimators proposed in offer a significant advantage in terms of their general applicability, making them a valuable tool for a broader range of problems in stress-strength reliability estimation. Furthermore, the technique discussed in this paper and the resulting estimators can be generalized to various sampling techniques, like, ranked set sampling, records data, Type I and Type II censored data. While we cannot directly apply the same estimators in such cases, we believe that conducting further studies in this field is of significant importance.

Table (1). Relative Bias (RB), relative root of mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the different estimators of R . The data are simulated from **paired normal** distributions.

(n_1, n_2)		\hat{R}_{MW}	\hat{R}_{JA}	\hat{R}_1	\hat{R}_2	\hat{R}_3
		Case (1), $R = 0.9192$				
(50, 50)	RB	0.0008	-0.0009	0.0001	-0.0005	-0.0002
	RMSE	0.0279	0.0273	0.0277	0.0274	0.0273
	EFF	1.000	1.047	1.013	1.039	1.045
(100, 200)	RB	-0.0004	-0.0009	-0.0006	-0.0008	-0.0007
	RMSE	0.0202	0.0193	0.0202	0.0193	0.0196
	EFF	1.000	1.099	1.001	1.098	1.064
		Case (2), $R = 0.3581$				
(50, 50)	RB	-0.0057	-0.0084	-0.0087	-0.0054	-0.0070
	RMSE	0.1686	0.1524	0.1525	0.1684	0.1564
	EFF	1.000	1.224	1.222	1.002	1.162
(100, 200)	RB	0.0008	0.0014	0.0013	0.0009	0.0011
	RMSE	0.0922	0.0806	0.0805	0.0921	0.0842
	EFF	1.000	1.310	1.310	1.003	1.199

Table (2). Relative Bias (RB), relative root of mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the different estimators of R . The data are simulated from **paired Weibul** distributions.

(n_1, n_2)		\hat{R}_{MW}	\hat{R}_{MC}	\hat{R}_1	\hat{R}_2	\hat{R}_3
		Case (1), $R = 0.9091$				
(50, 50)	RB	-0.0019	-0.0020	-0.0017	-0.0021	-0.0019
	RMSE	0.0336	0.0185	0.0332	0.0186	0.0231
	EFF	1.000	3.24	1.008	3.21	2.083
(100, 200)	RB	0.0001	-0.0005	0.0003	-0.0005	-0.0001
	RMSE	0.0222	0.0113	0.0220	0.0113	0.0145
	EFF	1.000	3.86	1.011	3.850	2.319
		Case (2), $R = 0.2857$				
(50, 50)	RB	0.0059	0.0109	0.0165	-0.0004	0.0081
	RMSE	0.1866	0.1482	0.1545	0.1814	0.1590
	EFF	1.000	1.584	1.459	1.058	1.376
(100, 200)	RB	-0.0025	-0.0021	-0.0003	-0.0045	-0.0024
	RMSE	0.1039	0.0865	0.0889	0.1020	0.0914
	EFF	1.000	1.444	1.367	1.038	1.293

Table (3). Relative Bias (RB), relative root of mean square error (RMSE) and efficiency (EFF) of the different estimators of R . The data are simulated from **paired generalized-Pareto** distributions.

(n_1, n_2)		\hat{R}_{MW}	\hat{R}_{RE}	\hat{R}_1	\hat{R}_2	\hat{R}_3
Case (1), R = 0.8889						
(50, 50)	RB	-0.0002	-0.0007	0.0002	-0.0009	-0.0004
	RMSE	0.0374	0.0226	0.0369	0.0227	0.0269
	EFF	1.000	2.740	1.024	2.710	1.932
(100, 200)	RB	-0.0017	-0.0012	-0.0016	-0.0013	-0.0015
	RMSE	0.0262	0.0135	0.0260	0.0136	0.0176
	EFF	1.000	3.740	1.011	3.720	2.217
Case (1), R = 0.3333						
(50, 50)	RB	-0.0026	-0.0009	0.0019	-0.0046	-0.0014
	RMSE	0.1612	0.1302	0.1345	0.1572	0.1387
	EFF	1.000	1.533	1.438	1.052	1.352
(100, 200)	RB	0.0037	0.0016	0.0050	0.0005	0.0027
	RMSE	0.0947	0.0812	0.0839	0.0918	0.0847
	EFF	1.000	1.361	1.275	1.064	1.250

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